

Cerebroplacental ratio prediction of intrapartum fetal compromise according to the interval to delivery

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What does this study add to current knowledge?

Our results showed a relationship between cerebroplacental ratio ability to predict cesarean section for intrapartum compromise and interval to delivery. The best prediction was done prior to labor and including estimated fetal weight and type of labor onset.

What are the main clinical implications?

Prediction of cesarean section for intrapartum compromise by means of cerebroplacental ratio should be done in the short term and adding the information provided by estimated fetal weight and type of labor onset.

ABSTRACT

Introduction

A controversy exists about the accuracy of the cerebroplacental ratio (CPR) for the prediction of cesarean section for intrapartum fetal compromise (CS-IFC). Our aim was to evaluate whether the interval to delivery modifies the accuracy of CPR either as a single marker or combined with estimated fetal weight centile (EFWc), type of labor onset (TLO) and other clinical variables.

Methods

This was a multicenter retrospective study of 5193 women with singleton pregnancies who underwent an ultrasound scan at 35⁺⁰- 41⁺⁰ weeks and gave birth within one month of examination, at any of the participating hospitals in Spain, UK, and Italy. CS-IFC was diagnosed in case of abnormal intrapartum fetal heart rate or intrapartum fetal scalp pH<7.20, requiring urgent cesarean section. The diagnostic ability of CPR in multiples of the median (CPR MoM) was evaluated at different intervals to delivery, alone and combined with EFWc, TLO, and other pregnancy data such as maternal age, maternal body mass index, parity, and fetal sex, for the prediction of CS-IFC by means of ROC curves and logistic regression analysis.

Results

The predictive ability of CPR MoM for CS-IFC worsened with the interval to delivery. In general, the best prediction was obtained prior to labor, and adding information related with EFWc and TLO [AUC 0.71 (95% CI 0.64-0.79), 0.73 (95% CI 0.66-0.80) and 0.75 (95% CI 0.69-0.81); P<0.0001]. Addition of more clinical data did not improve prediction. In addition, results did not vary when only cases with spontaneous onset of labor were studied.

Conclusion

CPR MoM prediction of CS-IFC at the end of pregnancy worsens with the interval to delivery. Accordingly, it should be done in the short term and considering EFWc and TLO.

INTRODUCTION

In contrast with early-onset fetal growth restriction (FGR), late-onset FGR is caused by an imbalance between fetal demands and placental supply, which tends to induce a kind of oxygenation failure [1] prior to the occurrence of any significant decrease in fetal size. Consequently, hypoxia and stillbirth may occur unexpectedly in appropriate for gestational age (AGA) fetuses that do not reach their growth potential [2,3,4], while on the other extreme, small fetuses with uneventful pregnancies may be constitutionally small [5].

Prompted by the inaccuracy of estimated fetal weight (EFW), the focus of interest has currently shifted from a ponderal perspective towards a prediction of outcome by means of cerebroplacental ratio (CPR). The advantage of CPR, which has emerged as an optimal determinant of adverse outcome at the end of pregnancy, is that it shows the imbalance between fetal demand and placental supply, reflecting cerebral vasodilation in response to hypoxaemia [6,7]. As this phenomenon may occur in theory at all weight centiles, CPR can be considered a marker of failure to reach growth potential regardless of fetal growth [3,4].

Previous works have studied the ability of CPR in detecting fetuses at risk prior to delivery [2, 8-11]. The majority agrees with the existence of a clear relationship between low CPR and adverse outcome, like neonatal hypoxia or cesarean section for intrapartum fetal compromise (CS-IFC), being the main difference the diagnostic ability and the prediction accuracy. A controversy that might be partially explained by the different intervals to labor included. Unfortunately, despite the interval importance has been earlier suggested [12], no study has clarified this relation in depth. The aim of this work was to evaluate the influence of this interval on the ability of CPR to predict

CS-IFC in the last month of pregnancy, alone or combined with other sonographic and clinical parameters.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This was a retrospective observational study including 5193 fetuses attending the day hospital and ultrasound units of several referral centers in Spain, Italy, and the UK. The ultrasound examinations were performed between 35+0 and 41+0 weeks in an heterogeneous population of fetuses attending the clinics for different surveillance purposes, including routine follow-up. Fetuses were assessed with Doppler ultrasound which included an estimated fetal weight and a Doppler evaluation of the umbilical (UA) and middle cerebral arteries (MCA) pulsatility indices (PI). The UA and MCA were recorded using color and pulse Doppler according to earlier descriptions [13-14], and the CPR was calculated as the simple ratio between the MCA PI and the UA PI [13,15]. Examinations were performed using General Electric Voluson® (E8/E6/730) ultrasound machines with 2-8 MHz convex probes, during fetal quiescence, in the absence of fetal tachycardia, and keeping the insonation angle with the examined vessels as small as possible.

Gestational age (GA) was determined according to the crown-rump length in the first trimester. To adjust for the effect of GA on fetal measurements and be able to make comparisons, EFW and birth weight (BW) were converted into centiles adjusting only for fetal gender. However, in interest of simplicity, we used the same reference for all the study population regardless of the country of origin [16]. Finally, for the same purpose CPR values were converted into multiples of the median (MoM) dividing each value by the 50th centile (median) at each GA, as earlier described [13]. CPR medians were those used in recent studies and were represented by the equation [13]:

CPR 50th centile = $-3.814786276 + 0.36363249 * GA \text{ (in weeks)} - 0.005646672 * GA \text{ (in weeks)}^2$.

Multiple pregnancies and those complicated by congenital fetal abnormalities or aneuploidies were excluded from the study. In addition, scheduled cesareans were also discarded, as we were specifically interested in outcome during labor progression.

The resulting group of fetuses represented a third level hospital population and consequently was heterogeneous, with both, normal appropriate-for-gestational-age fetuses attended for routine purposes, and fetuses with a variety of complications such as hypertensive diseases, diabetes, fetal growth restriction, etc.

All fetuses were delivered within one month after the scan. Therefore, examinations were always performed before premature rupture of membranes, onset of contractions, and any other circumstance leading to labor.

Outcome data including BW, mode of delivery, Apgar score and cord arterial pH were collected after birth. Onset of labor occurred for obstetric reasons and fetuses were managed according to their progression at labor [18]. CS-IFC was defined in case of abnormal intrapartum fetal heart rate [17] or intrapartum fetal scalp pH [19] requiring urgent cesarean section.

Descriptive statistics were performed evaluating maternal age, pre-pregnancy weight, height, body mass index, parity and number of gestations, plus GA at examination (in weeks), GA at delivery (in weeks), interval between ultrasound and delivery, EFW, EFW centile, BW, BW centile, UA PI MoM, MCA PI MoM, CPR MoM, fetal gender, type of labor onset (induction and spontaneous), mode of delivery (assisted and spontaneous vaginal delivery, cesarean section due to failure to progress and CS-IFC Apgar scores at 5 minutes, and neonatal cord arterial pH. Continuous variables were presented as median and interquartile range (IQR), while categorical variables were presented as absolute and relative frequencies.

The diagnostic ability of CPR MoM and EFW centile for the detection of CS-IFC was evaluated and compared according to the different intervals to labor using the ROC curves. To investigate the effect of the interval to delivery, 4 intervals to labor were evaluated: 0-1, 2-7, 8-14 and 15-30 days. At each interval, ROC curves provided the prediction accuracy. This was also calculated for three models representing three combinations of parameters: model 1 which included CPR MoM and EFWc, model 2 which included CPR MoM, EFWc and type of labor onset and model 3 which included CPR MoM, EFWc, type of labor onset and other clinical data. Finally, to give a general perspective, the prediction ability within one month of delivery was calculated for the CPR MoM, EFWc, and the three studied models, calculating the ROC curves with their detection rates (DR) (sensitivity) for a false positive rate (FPR) (1-specificity) of 10% and 5%.

Comparisons between groups in the descriptive analysis were made with Mann-Whitney U test for continuous data and Chi Square test for frequency data. Statistics were calculated with StatPlus® for Mac, version 7, and GraphPad Prism® for Mac version 5. Significance was established at P-value <0.05.

RESULTS

The characteristics of the study population are shown in Table 1. In summary, the study included 5193 singleton pregnancies, of which half 50.2% were male. The majority had an induced onset of labor (53.5%) reflecting the high risk nature of the population, and a spontaneous vaginal delivery (59%). Most of the inductions were due to anomalies of growth such as smallness for gestational age (SGA), postdates pregnancy, and premature rupture of membranes; 0.6% had an Apgar score <7 at 5 minutes and 2.3% a neonatal cord pH <7.20. Abnormal intrapartum fetal heart rate or intrapartum scalp pH (<7.20) requiring emergency cesarean section (CS-IFC) were recorded in 5.7% of fetuses, while 25.7% had a birth weight below the 10th centile.

Table 2 compares the characteristics of the pregnancies according to the studied outcome (CS-IFC). In the adverse outcome group, BMI ($P<0.001$) and UA PI MoM were significantly higher ($P<0.0001$) while GA at examination, GA at delivery, maternal height, parity, and number of gestations, EFW, EFWc, BW, BW centile, MCA PI MoM, CPR MoM, Apgar at 5 minutes and arterial cord pH were significantly lower ($P<0.0001$). In addition, there were significantly more SGA fetuses, and inductions of labor ($P<0.0001$). No differences were observed concerning maternal age and maternal pre-pregnancy weight.

Figure 1 shows the ROC curves representing the accuracy of CPR MoM and EFWc at the four different intervals to delivery (0-1, 2-7, 8-14, 15-30 days). The best prediction was obtained in both cases prior to labor [AUC 0.71 (95% CI 0.64-0.79), and 0.68 (95% CI 0.62-0.75); $P<0.0001$]. In addition, despite the absence of significance at higher intervals, a trend to a lower accuracy with higher intervals can be observed.

Figure 2 shows the ROC curves representing the accuracy of the three models at the four intervals studied. Model 1, which combined CPR MoM and EFWc obtained at 0-1

and 2-7 days better predictions than any of its components [AUC= 0.73 (95% CI 0.66-0.80) and 0.66 (95% CI 0.61-0.71); $P<0.0001$]. Model 2, which included the type of labor onset obtained even better predictions [AUC 0.75 (95% CI 0.69-0.81), 0.67 (95% CI 0.62-0.72), 0.68 (95% CI 0.60-0.76), and 0.58 (95% CI 0.51-0.65), at 0-1, 2-7, 8-14 and 15-30 days, respectively; $P<0.0001$]. Its predictive accuracy was not improved by the addition of more clinical data (model 3).

Figure 3 and table 3 show the individual and combined models and the ROC curves representing the overall accuracy for the prediction of CS-IFC within one month of delivery. The model that combined CPR MoM and EFWc (model 1) obtained better accuracies [0.64, (95% CI 0.61-0.68); $P<0.0001$] than the individual parameters CPR MoM and EFWc by themselves [0.61, (95% CI 0.58-0.65) and 0.63 (95% CI 0.59-0.66); $P<0.0001$]. In addition, the model that included the type of labor onset (model 2) obtained the best accuracy [AUC 0.68, (95% CI 0.65-0.71); $P<0.0001$] and was not improved by addition of other clinical data (model 3) [AUC 0.68, (95% CI 0.65-0.71); $P<0.0001$].

Finally, to discard intervention bias, figure 4 shows the prediction ability of CPR MoM and CPR MoM + EFWc in 2625 pregnancies with an spontaneous onset of labor. In this case, the first group included cases with an 0-7 days interval. The phenomenon above indicated persisted, and a higher accuracy was still present in cases with lower interval examination-delivery, although due to the lower number of cases, statistical significance was determined only at the lowest interval.

DISCUSSION

Summary of key findings

Our results showed a close relationship between CPR ability to predict CS-IFC and interval to delivery. The best prediction was done prior to labor and including EFW data and TLO.

Interpretation of study findings and comparison with published literature

Despite most of CS-IFC at the end of pregnancy occur in appropriate for gestational age fetuses [20-2], prediction of CS-IFC has been influenced by a ponderal approach in which only small fetuses were supposed to be at risk. Prediction by means of CPR has emerged as a hemodynamic alternative to EFW, in fetuses with normal and abnormal growth [3], that is able to improve the predictive accuracy in mathematical [23] and clinical [24] models without the help of other hemodynamic parameters like the uterine artery Doppler [25].

Interestingly, while the evidence of an association between CPR and adverse outcome is out of doubt [26-31] the controversy persists regarding CPR accuracy: for some authors it is good (AUC= 0.96 [32], 0.88 [33] and 0.723 [34,35]), while for others it is moderate (AUC 0.69) [36] or even very low [37]. In this study we inquired whether a different interval to labor might be partially the cause of this difference. Our results demonstrated that the interval to outcome was able to modify the predictive accuracy. Not only in case of CPR but also in case of EFW, and that the combination of CPR and EFW, ameliorated the effect of the interval thus increasing accuracy. Interestingly, the best prediction of CS-IFC was obtained when data referred to the onset of labor were also included. Probably because many inductions were related with fetal conditions increasing the possibility of CS-IFC and as a result of the effort needed to overcome the resistance to cervical effacement, as recently suggested [38].

Unfortunately, although the effect of combining EFW and CPR for the prediction of adverse outcome was earlier described [39], we were not able to find earlier works evaluating the effect of the interval to delivery on CS-IFC prediction, and therefore could not compare our data with previous reports.

From a mathematical point of view, any interval to prediction is an important determinant of accuracy, however, in case of CPR it is probably not the only cause explaining differences in accuracy between different groups, as some groups have also suggested poor accuracies prior to labor [37,40]. A different examination methodology might explain these differences in part, and mismatches in outcome description might also account for a proportion of such variation.

Research and clinical implications

According to our results, to perform comparative studies referred to CPR MoM it should be mandatory to specify the interval to labor, as the existence of different mean intervals might prevent drawing significant conclusions. Also, from a clinical perspective, prediction of CS-IFC by means of CPR MoM should be done in the short term, and considering EFWc and TLO, as both parameters influence the advent of CS-IFC. This might be important in the management of fetuses at the end of pregnancy, and when faced with the dilemma of prolonging pregnancy a few days beyond the day of examination [41], as pregnancies with normal CPR, appropriate EFW and spontaneous onset of labor might be less likely to show unexpected adverse outcome.

Strengths and limitations

The strengths of the study are its novelty, as this is the first work assessing the influence of the interval to labor on the predictive accuracy of CPR for CS-IFC, and the accuracy of the statistical methodology. Conversely, limitations include the relatively low number of cases, which made necessary the use of arbitrary intervals, the

retrospective nature of the study, the heterogeneity of the study population also evaluated at different hospital settings, the application of the same population references to different countries, the lack of study of maternal morbidities, the impossibility to determine with precision the interval to delivery and last but not least, the possibility of intervention bias. In fact, we were especially concerned about the last issue, as babies delivered with CS-IFC presented smaller intervals to delivery and higher proportions of inductions. However, for ethical reasons it was not possible to hide the examination to managing clinicians. A way to evaluate the existence of intervention bias was to study the accuracy only in fetuses with spontaneous onset of labor. We made a simplified analysis in 2625 cases without induction on labor and results persisted, proving that even the existence of an intervention bias was not responsible for the entire prediction improvement observed in cases with lower intervals.

Conclusion

While information provided by EFW and type of labor onset might improve accuracy, prediction of CS-IFC by means of CPR should be done in the short term. In this scenario, fetuses with low EFW and low CPR, especially if undergoing induction, should be considered at risk of adverse outcome.

Statement of Ethics.

An IRB permission was obtained for the study (Comisión de Investigación del Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria La Fe, reference 2014/0063). Being a retrospective study, the requirement for informed consent, was waived by the IRB and there was no need to include it in the study.

Conflict of Interest Statement.

The authors report no conflicts of interest.

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Authors' contributions.

José Morales-Roselló designed the study, performed part of the ultrasound examinations, did the statistical analysis, and wrote the manuscript.

Asma Khalil supervised the final manuscript and made notable contributions to the final text.

Gabriela Loscalzo, Silvia Buongiorno, Maia Brik, Manel Mendoza, Carolina Di Fabrizio, Scarinci Elisa, Silvia Salvi, performed some of the ultrasound examinations collected data and suggested valuable inputs to the text.

Antonio Lanzone and Alfredo Perales-Marín, supervised the final manuscript and suggested valuable inputs to the text.

Data Availability Statement.

The data that support the findings of this study are filed in the hospital database, and are available from the corresponding author, JMR, upon request.

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FIGURES

Figure 1.

Predictive accuracy of CPR MoM and EFW centile classified according to the interval to labor.

Figure 2.

Predictive accuracy of three studied models, classified according to the interval to delivery. Model 1 combines CPR MoM and EFW centile. Model 2 combines CPR MoM, EFW centile and type of labor onset. Finally, model 3 combines CPR MoM, EFW centile, type of labor onset (need for induction) and several clinical data.

Figure 3.

Overall predictive accuracy for CS-IFC within one month of delivery.

Figure 4.

Prediction ability of CPR MoM and CPR MoM + EFWc in 2625 pregnancies with an spontaneous onset of labor. In this case, due to the lower number of cases, the first group included examinations with an 0-7 days interval. A higher accuracy is still present in cases with lower interval examination-delivery.

Detection of CS-IFC, according to interval to delivery

Detection of CS-IFC, according to interval to delivery

Overall prediction of CS-IFC
within 1 month of delivery

Detection of CS-IFC, according to interval to delivery
in fetuses that started labour spontaneously

